

Idiomatism and Performance Aspects in the Use of the Berimbau in Two Solo Works

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Abstract

This article examines the berimbau, a percussion instrument deeply rooted in Brazilian popular and traditional culture, within the context of concert music. The recital featured two solo works by Brazilian composers—*Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” by Rodrigo Lima and *Íris* by Alexandre Lunsqui—which explore the technical, timbral, and expressive potential of the berimbau. These compositions expand the instrument’s techniques and idiom, highlighting its role beyond traditional contexts and fostering a dialogue between popular music and concert music. The study also analyzes the characteristics of the works, their references, and the challenges posed to performers. By engaging with non-conventional instrumentations, this research contributes to the training of percussionists interested in exploring Brazilian instruments within the contemporary repertoire. The use of the berimbau in these pieces encourages an encounter between musical traditions, inviting performers to engage with the expressive and symbolic layers of an instrument deeply connected to Afro-Brazilian heritage. The project investigates how this dialogue enriches both the performer and the repertoire, opening new interpretative and technical pathways.

On the Research, the Berimbau, and Idiomatism

The use of percussion instruments associated with Brazilian popular and traditional music within the context of concert music has been steadily increasing. This article analyzes the berimbau from different perspectives of performance in two Brazilian solo percussion works: *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” by Rodrigo Lima and *Íris* by Alexandre Lunsqui. The particularities of the instrument, its modes of execution, and interpretative solutions for the new idiomatic proposals formulated by each composer are discussed.

From these contrasting approaches, this research addresses possible paths toward a fully developed interpretation, considering how composers bring timbres from Brazilian popular music into a new language and, consequently, into a new context. This process fosters encounters between different musical genres and encourages investigations into performers’ training profiles, the techniques required, and the challenges inherent in this repertoire. The study thus reflects on the trajectory of the concert music performer when engaging with an instrument laden with elements and ancestral ties to popular culture, analyzing the relationship between these contexts and their role in expanding both the instrumental idiom and the performer’s technical–performative repertoire.

When consulting the description of the berimbau in Mário D. Frungillo's *Dicionário de Percussão* (2003), it becomes evident that the author initially presents capoeira as the musical genre in which the instrument is most frequently employed, as illustrated in the following excerpt:

Berimbau, a struck chordophone. . . identified with the dance-game of capoeira, has been sporadically used in Western art music. In capoeira, at least one instrument is used, and in Angola-style capoeira three are employed, known as gunga (low), médio (middle), and viola (high), generally with sizes corresponding to pitch height . . .

—Frungillo (2003, p. 39, translation by the author)

Due to the lack of historical documentation, it is not possible to determine precisely when the berimbau became associated with capoeira; however, by the early twentieth century it was already part of this practice and had become its symbol. Kay Shaffer, in *O Berimbau-de-barriga e seus toques*, describes the berimbau as a musical bow, stating that “in general, it is constructed from a flexible piece of wood held in an arched shape by a steel wire, with a gourd attached to the lower part. It is played together with a caxixi—a type of rattle” (Shaffer 1977, p. 20). Traditional mastery of the berimbau proved fundamental to the interpretation of the works analyzed. Prior knowledge of the instrument’s assembly and tuning, technique, timbre, and characteristic gesturality provided a concrete reference from which it was possible to understand the alternative explorations proposed in the compositions. This traditional experience consolidated a bodily and sonic memory that guided the adaptation to new materials—such as different mallets, suspension methods, the use of objects, and extended sound exploration—allowing these demands to be interpreted with control, coherence, and idiomatic sensitivity, even outside the berimbau’s original cultural context.

Figure 1: The berimbau and its accessories. Photograph by the author.

Figure 1 indicates each element that constitutes the berimbau. The wooden bow is known as the verga, and the baqueta (stick) may be made from the same wood as the verga. The figure also shows the dobrão, a large coin which, in traditional performance practice, is held between the thumb and index finger, in the same hand that supports

the instrument with the middle, ring, and little fingers. The coin is used to tension the string, causing it to sound a pitch one tone higher than the open string, which may also be achieved using a small, smooth stone.

The works by Lima and Lunsqui are also analyzed from the perspective of berimbau idiom. According to Pavan (2009, p. 39), as cited in Miranda (2018, p. 15), “in the etymological origin of the word idiomatic, *idio* derives from the Greek *ídios*, meaning that which is proper, personal, or distinctive.” In musical research, the term may refer to the characteristics inherent to a particular instrument or style. Thus, instrumental idiom encompasses:

the peculiarities and technical and expressive possibilities that a given sound medium affords. . . Among the aspects covered by the term are: specific performance techniques; physical and mechanical possibilities; expressive potential; typical compositional procedures; the level of feasibility of such procedures; and knowledge of relevant works for the medium, among others

—Kreutz (2012, p. 3), as cited in Miranda (2018, p. 16, translation by the author).

By articulating traditional practice, idiomatic characterization, and the insertion of the berimbau into concert music, this study delineates the parameters that guide the present investigation. These elements serve as a foundation for interpreting the technical and expressive demands proposed by Lima and Lunsqui, as well as for understanding the construction of a specific instrumental idiom that emerges from the dialogue between tradition and contemporary musical language. The following sections analyzes *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” and *Íris*, highlighting the compositional and performative procedures that reconfigure the berimbau in each work, in addition to proposing practical solutions that enabled their performance according to the composers’ demands.

The Berimbau in *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” and *Íris*

Composed in 2013, *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” presents the berimbau as the leading instrument, responsible for the exposition of the thematic material and for providing the compositional material that structures the entire work. Written for multiple percussion, the piece employs a suspended berimbau in combination with a pair of bongos, a low-pitched drum, a metal reco-reco, a Thai gong, and two Chinese gongs. The rhythmic cycles, inspired by Indian talas, are introduced in the opening measures through the berimbau and recur at various moments in the other instruments.

In the performance notes of the score, the composer specifies that the berimbau must be suspended for the execution of the work, leaving it to the performer to determine the form and mechanism used for this suspension. In our setup, we used a bongo stand to support the instrument; however, we identified the need to avoid direct contact between the wood of the berimbau and the metal of the stand, as such contact would dampen its resonance and alter its characteristic timbre. For this reason, we suggest covering the metal surface with rubber or foam only in the area that comes into contact with the wooden bow of the suspended instrument. Figure 2 documents the final setup adopted for the performance of the work:

Figure 2: Setup for *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*”. Source: Authors’ archive.

Figure 2 also shows the positioning of the berimbau’s gourd (*cabaça*) oriented laterally in relation to the instrument, directing the sound toward the audience and ensuring that its volume is not lost amid the drums and gongs, which have greater sound projection. In the first measure of the work, Lima indicates that the berimbau may be played with the wooden shaft of the mallets. However, during our investigations, we observed that a standard multiple-percussion mallet has excessive weight for the instrument’s string, increasing the risk of breakage—a situation that occurred several times during the early stages of practice. As a solution, we opted to use a stick specifically designed for playing the berimbau. Its lighter weight, combined with striking the string as close as possible to the *cabaça*, preserves the instrument’s characteristic timbre without compromising the integrity of the string, while also facilitating the production of the fundamental pitch corresponding to the berimbau’s tuning.

We observed that the compositional demands of the work require the simultaneous use of four mallets, enabling the performance of instruments with different classifications and timbral qualities, as well as the execution of complex passages. The Leigh Howard Stevens technique (Stevens 1979), which avoids crossing the mallets, proved to be the most suitable for playing the berimbau, as it allows greater freedom and fluidity of movement, in addition to a more efficient rebound. For the drums, gongs, and wood block, the Gary Burton technique (Burton 1965)—characterized by crossed mallets—proved more effective, providing greater stability for rapid passages between the drums. Thus, two distinct techniques are employed simultaneously in sections 1 and 3, where the berimbau is present, while in the intermediate section, without the berimbau, the metal *reco-reco* is also played using the Burton technique in order to achieve greater agility and control.

The solutions proposed for the performance of *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” highlight the exploration of the berimbau through a structural logic based on rhythmic cycles and its integration into a multiple-percussion setup, underscoring both the technical complexity of this transposition and the expressive versatility of the instrument. From these con-

siderations, the discussion moves to the analysis of *Íris*, a work in which the compositional treatment of the berimbau unfolds according to different aesthetic and gestural premises.

Composed in 2012, *Íris* employs the berimbau exclusively, exploring a wide range of techniques and interpretative resources. A wooden stick, a grooved metal stick (“parafuso”) for scraping, stones, a metal tube, a bamboo reco-reco, a caxixi, and a cord used to suspend the instrument on the performer’s body are employed according to the composer’s demands. The work expands the berimbau’s timbral possibilities by incorporating sound explorations, harmonic sounds, and unconventional methods of sound sustain, while simultaneously integrating traditional techniques and sound practices associated with the instrument.

Preparing the berimbau became essential for the feasibility of the work. During our studies, we identified the need to glue a small piece of sandpaper between the cabaça and the wooden bow in order to prevent the gourd from slipping and consequently causing detuning due to the intense movements characteristic of the performance. A more resistant wire also proved to be more suitable for withstanding the strikes and scraping gestures with the metal stick. In Brazil, most capoeira masters and berimbau makers use wire extracted from car tyres; however, we obtained wire extracted from truck tyres, which proved to be more resistant and better suited to the purposes of both works discussed here.

Figure 3: Setup for *Íris*. Source: Authors’ archive.

In *Íris*, Lunsqui does not explicitly suggest that the berimbau be suspended; nevertheless, from the very beginning of the piece, the notation for the right-hand stick played simultaneously with the left hand striking the cabaça with the fingers indicates the need to suspend the instrument in a way that does not compromise its natural resonance. The setup illustrated in Figure 3 shows the different sticks and objects used in the work, as well as the cord employed to suspend the instrument around the performer’s neck, allowing the use of both hands throughout the performance:

Figure 3 also shows two stones placed on the table to the performer’s left, which allow

the execution of the three pitches prescribed by the composer for the berimbau string—a technique that does not exist in the instrument’s traditional performance practice. In this way, it becomes possible to produce different pitches without the need to support the berimbau by holding it with the left hand, while simultaneously maintaining the two stones between the thumb/index and index/middle fingers, ensuring the instrument’s characteristic resonance. We also emphasize the importance of using porous stones or stones with some degree of surface grip, in order to prevent slipping due to perspiration during performance. This ensures the precise tension point required for each pitch on the string, while also allowing the necessary balance to hold the instrument simultaneously.

Some resources derived from the traditional manner of playing the berimbau are also incorporated into the work’s requirements, such as striking the string with the tip of the wooden stick to extract the lowest sound, characterized by the presence of the instrument’s fundamental pitch. To achieve this, it is likewise necessary to play as close as possible to the point of contact with the cabaça. The use of the caxixi, a complementary instrument traditionally associated with the berimbau, is also present in the work, appearing at a climactic moment that leads to the conclusion. In this same passage, the composer indicates the use of the dobrão, a metal coin traditionally employed in berimbau performance; however, this object does not produce the desired sonic glissando required by the piece. For this reason, we chose to replace the dobrão with a small metal tube, which allows for the production of a more audible and resonant sound. At the end of the work, the composer indicates the need for a grooved wooden stick to execute a roll on the cabaça. In our experiments, we found that using a thin bamboo reco-reco played along the rim of the cabaça not only produces the desired effect but also yields a more present and projected sound.

The interpretive practice of *Íris* demonstrates that the work requires from the performer a deep understanding of both traditional berimbau techniques and the new sonic possibilities proposed by Lunsqui. The specific preparation of the instrument, the use of non-conventional materials, and the need for suspension reveal a constant dialogue between tradition and experimentation. In this context, prior familiarity with the instrument proved essential to technical feasibility and to the construction of an interpretation consistent with the work’s hybrid language, establishing *Íris* as a significant example of the berimbau’s potential within the contemporary percussion repertoire.

Final Considerations

The works analyzed highlight the growing incorporation of the berimbau and other instruments rooted in Brazilian popular culture into the context of concert music, revealing new technical possibilities and fostering encounters between distinct cultural spheres. In *Matiz III*, “*Ciclos*” and *Íris*, traditional knowledge and practice of the berimbau proved fundamental to the development of viable interpretive solutions, supporting the transition toward expanded techniques and new sonic discourses. The process of adapting the instrument—through suspension, the selection of specific beaters, and the use of various objects—underscores detailed preparation as an essential component of

performance. In this sense, the works expand the performer's technical–performative repertoire and reaffirm the need for an interpretive approach that integrates tradition, innovation, and the aesthetic demands of contemporary music.

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